

Immunornase to degrading vaccines mRNA and prevents the formation of the proteotoxic effect related to the bias codon usage

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Abstract:

Now that mRNA vaccines have ended their sense phase, in preparation for which they were created and placed on the world market, now seemingly dissolved with the disappearance of a high incidence in infections and deaths due to Sars-CoV-2 virus, another research challenge arises: degrading the mRNA in those who received the inoculation, as they will surely have developed antibodies and immune response by now to be able to fight off any future exposure to the pathogen, but especially in regard to recent studies substantiating the possibility of detecting mRNA fragments or Spike protein within the body up to 6 months after the last vaccination, in addition to the various manifestations similar to those that have arisen as symptoms of Sars-CoV-2 disease, part of the syndrome referred to as Long-Covid, although nonspecific and of varying severity, has in some cases been the occurrence of clinically remarkable events. A Ribonuclease enzyme, called Ranpirnase, associated with a monoclonal antibody at the beginning of its introduction as a therapeutic option for a variety of purposes, derive from the ICSM18 mouse anti-PrPC antibody, called PRN100, was considered for this. The two elements, when combined, would form an engineered compound called Immunornase, capable of preventing the appearance of effects due to the production of unanticipated proteins by preventing their production and, at the same time, counteracting any iatrogenically symptomatic activity.

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I. INTRODUCTION

There is evidence that various **alterations** in the **genetic sequence** of the **mRNA** of the **Covid Pfizer** vaccine named **BNT162b2**, compared with the **genetic code** of the natural viral counterpart of **Sars-CoV-2**, cause a **high probability** by the organism's **ribosomal mechanism** to outcoming the striking serious **errors** in **reading, translating** the genetic sequence, and **executing a wrong instruction** contained in the mRNA, as demonstrated in the article by **Dr. Kira Smith** published **Feb. 5, 2021** on Longdom's *International Journal of Antivirals and Antiretrovirals*, later removed and still **available**, however, on *ResearchGate*^[1].

This was only the **first research paper** to **highlight** several factors capable of causing **problems** in the recipient organism of the **Covid vaccine**, but a huge number have been published over time, until the **recent noteworthy study** conducted by researchers at the **University of Cambridge**, published in **December 2023** on *Nature*, which demonstrates the occurrence of **ribosomal frameshifting +1** phenomenon *in vivo*; this indicates a general **lack** of overall **sequence stability** and, as a result, production of **elements** of **unknown** toxicity and functions, **other than** the designated **S Spike** protein^[2].

Although the researchers **claimed** to have found **no serious consequences** in humans, it is **unknown** whether it's really **harmless**, especially upon the occurrence of the above **abnormal** phenomenon **in conjunction** with other **risk factors** for global mRNA stability.

It's clear that **+1 ribosomal frameshifting** together with the presence of **rigid secondary structures** in the **mRNA** leads to allow **ribosomes** to easily **move** back and forth can cause **frameshifting** with **high frequency**, which result in strong **ribosome pausing** or **stalling** in

translation systems. In addition, ribosomal **stalling** can cause **premature translation termination**, thus **reducing** translation **efficiency**, that usually lead to early termination and **truncated protein** products.^[3]

Moreover, P-body transcriptome analyses suggest that **GC** content can influence **mRNA storage in P-bodies** and **mRNA decay** in human cells. Although **increased expression** is the desired outcome of codon optimization, it's necessary to control **over-expression** to avoid the **confounding** influence of **stress** on the **quality control** machinery of the **cell**. There are many studies suggesting that **ribosomal pauses** schedule **co-translational folding** of protein domains and determine the **final protein** conformation.^[4]

II. CODON BIAS USAGE AND NEW UNKNOWN PEPTIDES BORN

The **degeneracy** of genetic codons, predominantly due to **flexibility** in the identity of the **third nucleotide** —in what is known as the **wobble position**— allows 18 of the 20 **standard** amino acids to be encoded by two to six **synonymous** codons.^[3] Although the **genetic code** is almost **identical** in all organisms, the **preferential use** of certain **synonymous** codons is a phenomenon called **codon usage bias**.^[3]

Because synonymous **codon mutations** do **not change protein sequences**, synonymous codons were previously considered to be **redundant**, and their mutations were regarded as **silent mutations**^[3]. Many **human diseases** are associated with **silent SNPs**, but whether codon usage **changes** contribute to **human diseases** caused by these **SNPs** is still **not clear**, since it was shown that the **supposed** 'silent' mutations can have an impact on **human health** through various

mechanisms. One of these mechanisms is **protein misfolding**, which occurs by means of an **alteration** of the **ribosome-mediated translational** attenuation program.^[5]

The main idea underlying the **protein-misfolding** based mechanism, is that **codon usage** can modulate **ribosome traffic** and, consequently, **co-translational folding**, by means of associating frequent codons with **fast elongation rates** and rare codons with **slow elongation rates**. However, the **exact** mechanism connecting **proteostasis** with codon usage remains **unclear**.^[5]

In addition, there are potentially **serious consequences** associated with using **codon-optimization**, particularly for **nucleic acid therapeutics**. In the absence of analysis; these potential **problems** include: (I) disrupting the normal **patterns** of **cognate** and **wobble tRNA** usage, affecting **protein structure** and **function**; (II) producing **novel peptides** with **unknown** biological **activities**; and (III) altering **post-transcriptional modifications** that may modify **protein ensembles**.^[6]

Of note, **increased** protein **expression**, mediated by codon pair optimization, was reported to occur in the **absence** of **increased mRNA levels**, and there is evidence suggesting that **codon pair usage changes** may be involved in **human diseases**.^[7]

In a research article are reviewed **22 genetic diseases** or traits associated with **synonymous mutations**. It is known that the genetic condition for **multidrug resistance** is a consequence of the **protein-misfolding** based mechanism, whereas **three** other of **22 diseases** (Crohn's disease, cystic fibrosis and TMD) are the result of different mechanisms, but to **common root**.^[5] In addition, **tRNA quality** is also related to **tRNA modifications**, therefore, it will be worthwhile to examine the **effects** of tRNA

modifications on mRNA **stability**, since **tRNAs** are master **gene regulators** and highlight the need to fully understand how **tRNA expression** and processing are regulated in different **cells** and various conditions, including **human diseases**.^[8]

Given this background, it has been said it may prove **useful** to set out to find an **agent** that can **degrading mRNA** before it does irreparable **damages**.

III. PRIONS AND AMYLOIDS FORMATION PREDICTION

Yeast **prions** are the best understood transmissible **amyloids**. In these proteins, **prion formation** from an **initially soluble** state involves a **structural conversion**, driven, in many cases, by specific **domains enriched** in **glutamine/asparagine (Q/N)** residues. **PrionW** is a web application that exploits this principle to **scan sequences** in order to **identify proteins** containing **Q/N enriched prion-like domains (PrLDs)** in large datasets. A sub-set of prions, not including **PrP**, are **multidomain proteins** containing both **globular domains** and, usually, one **Prion Forming Domain (PFD)** enriched in **glutamine and asparagine (Q/N)** residues that undergoes the **structural rearrangement** during **prion** conversion. **Amyloid core identification and scoring**: the individual **sequences** fulfilling the requirements in various **steps** are further evaluated for the presence of a **21-residue long amyloid core** able to specifically nucleate **its self-assembly** according to the **pWALTZ scoring** function, an **update** of the **scoring** function in our well-established **amyloid predictor WALTZ**.^[9]

The best understood prions are from yeast and have a **prion-forming domain** with **strongly biased amino acid composition**, most notably

Among **mushrooms** class there are: *Agrocybe cylindracea*, from which was isolated **9.5-kDa** peptide, with RNase activity and antiproliferative effects on leukemia cell line and hepatoma cell line; *Hypsizigus marmoreus* from which is purified **18-kDa** RNase; many mushrooms of *Pleurotus* genus; *Cantharellus cibarius* associated with a ubiquitin-like peptide with ribonuclease activity (**Rnase III**) and many other species.

Among **bacterial** RNase the main is **Binase**, a **T1 RNase** member with many medical properties, that make it attractive for use in various ways. In addition, it's important the activity of the **exoribonucleases** from the human pathogen *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*.

In **plants** are observed RNases from *Panax Ginseng*, American and Chinese, but also wheat leaf, mung bean, black pine pollen, tomato and other minors.

The main **animal** RNases are: **Ranpirnase** (also called **Onconase**), containing **amphinase**, a RNase enzyme purified from oocytes of *Rana pipiens*; **BP-RNase** (Bovine Pancreatic Ribonuclease), **BS-RNase** (Bovine Seminal), **HP-RNase** (Human Pancreatic) and others.^[12]

V. DETECTION OF THE APPROPRIATE RNASE AGENT

At the end of this intricate research work, it has been established and demonstrated that the enzyme **Ranpirnase**, from the large class of protein named **ribonucleases (RNase)**, and it's able to perform the degradation of **BNT162b2** vaccine **mRNA**, **without** causing adverse **side effects** and **without** likelihood of lead to the onset of **pathological events** in any individual receiving its administration, since it is an **extracted** from the **Northern leopard frog**, *Rana pipiens*.

As a ribonuclease, **Ranpirnase** degrades breaking down **RNA** molecules in **cells**, and resulting in the **disruption** of **protein translation** and **apoptosis**; since cells with **higher levels** of **tRNA** than normal cells, such as **cancer cells**, are more susceptible to the effects of **Ranpirnase**, its **anticancer properties** have been studied^[13], with a view to **future applications** in this field. However, it is observable the **effectiveness** of the application aimed at **degrading exogenous mRNA**, preventing the **formation** of harmful elements, such as **prions** and **amyloids**.

The pathways affected by **Ranpirnase** also include **MAPK** signalling, **cytokine-cytokine-receptor** interactions and **Jak-STAT** signalling.^[14]

Ranpirnase has affinity especially for **Guanine** and **Uracil**, so it's optimal in its use for the purpose of **BNT162b2 mRNA** degradation, because of the **choices** made during gene sequence **optimization** and the extensive **codon bias usage**, employing for each **triplet** the amino acid **synonym** containing **C** or **G**, which demonstrates the **abundant** presence of **Guanine** to encode most amino acids.^[15]

VI. RANPIRNASE ENZYME DEPLOYMENT

The enzyme **Ranpirnase** acts on **errors** in the **structure** of an **mRNA**, **degrading** it. The **enzyme** recognises specific **features** or **defects** in the **mRNA** structure, such as the presence of **loops** or **mismatched regions**, and **catalyses** their degradation. This degradation process is important for maintaining the **integrity** and **quality** of **cellular mRNA** by eliminating **defective** or **poorly structured** mRNA. The enzyme **Ranpirnase** plays a key role in mRNA quality **control**, contributing to the selective **removal** of **mRNAs** with **structural errors**, which could lead to the production of **malfunctioning** or **non-functional proteins**.

The enzyme *Ranpirnase* may play an **indirect** role in **preventing** the formation of **amyloids** and **prions**.

Amyloids are insoluble **protein aggregates** that can be formed by **misfolded proteins** or proteins with structure errors. **Prions**, on the other hand, are **subclass** of **amyloid** with the ability to propagate *in vivo*, thus becoming **infectious**; they are **abnormal proteins** that can cause **neurodegenerative** diseases such as *Creutzfeldt-Jakob* disease.

Since the enzyme *Ranpirnase* is involved in the **degradation** of **defective** or **poorly structured mRNAs**, it can help remove mRNAs that code for **proteins** with structure **errors**. By removing these **defective mRNAs**, the *Ranpirnase* enzyme can indirectly **reduces** the production of **abnormal proteins** and thus prevents the **formation** of amyloids and prions.

However, it's important to emphasise that the **formation** of **amyloids** and **prions** is a **complex process** influenced by many factors. The enzyme *Ranpirnase* may play a key role in **preventing** such formations, but **it's not** the **only factor** involved.

The indicated **dosage** ranges from **30 mcg/kg** to **120 mcg/kg**, administered via **intravenous** route, **once** a day, for **3-5 consecutive days**, with a **withdrawal** period of **9-16 days**. This **cicle** should be **repeated** at least a **second time** in those manifesting initial **non-critical** symptoms, while those showing a **severe** clinical condition should **repeat** treatment a **3rd time**, followed by an **observation** period.^[16]

However, it must be acknowledged that a **fair** amount of **time** has passed since the **introduction** of **mRNA vaccines**, so many who have received it **no longer** retain the **mRNA** in the body, although it has been shown that some **fragments** can be **found** even **6 months** later, so it is also necessary to **counteract** unknown and potentially **harmful**

peptides already produced by **ribosomes**, based on the **instructions** originally contained in the **mRNA** and as a result of which **reading**, **translation**, or **execution errors** were made; it is incumbent, therefore, to neutralize the **pathological** symptoms of the entry into the body, once released from the cytoplasm, of **harmful proteins**, analogous or exactly identical to **prions** and **amyloids**.

In this regard, when an **additional** effect beyond **RNase** activity is desired, a **monoclonal antibody** is **combined** with the enzyme, as in the case of the compound **scFv 4D5-dibarnase**, although it has been developed through **biomedical engineering** to target certain forms of **cancer**.^[12]

One such compound which conjugates a monoclonal antibody to a ribonuclease agent is named **Immunornase**.

Fig. 3: Ribnuclease typologies

VII. MONOCLONAL ANTIBODY ACTIVITY IN PRION DISEASE AND AMYLOIDOSIS

The currently most promising **anti-PrPC monoclonal antibody** in the fight against **prion diseases** is **PRN100**, a mouse derivative of the **ICSM18** antibody, **discovered** in the early **2000s** and later “humanized”, due to the **promising** proprieties of prion **propagation inhibition** noticed.

In **2022**, the study regarding the **first trial in humans** was published, which took place **from 2018 to 2019**, with results which boded well, especially for a patient diagnosed with **iatrogenic CJD**, who continued the treatment for **140 days** demonstrating a greater **slowdown** in **neurodegenerative** symptoms than the control method.

Were treated **six patients** (two men; four women) with **CJD** for **7–260 days** at **UCLH** between Oct 9, 2018, and July 31, 2019. Repeated **intravenous** dosing of **PRN100** was **well tolerated** and reached the target **CSF drug concentration** (50 nM) in **four** patients after **22–70** days; **no** clinically **significant adverse reactions** were seen. All patients showed progressive neurological **decline** on serial assessments with the **MRC Scales**. Neuropathological **examination** was done in two patients (patients 2 and 3) and showed **no evidence** of **cytotoxicity**. Patient 2, who was treated for **140 days**, had the **longest** clinical **duration** we have yet documented for **iatrogenic CJD** and showed patterns of **disease-associated PrP** that differed from untreated patients with CJD, consistent with drug effects. Patient 3, who had **sporadic CJD** and only received **one therapeutic dose** of 80 mg/kg, had weak PrP synaptic labelling in the **periventricular** regions, which was not a feature of untreated patients with sporadic CJD. Brain tissue-bound **drug concentrations** across **multiple regions** in patient 2 ranged from **9.9 µg per g** of tissue (SD 0.3) in the **thalamus** to **27.4 µg per g** of tissue (1.5) in the **basal ganglia** (equivalent to 66–182 nM).^[17]

These are the **conclusions**:

Although disease progression was not halted or reversed in any patient, MRC Prion Disease Rating Scale scores did appear to stabilise in three patients for periods when CSF drug concentrations reached the target concentration, but the small number of patients precluded meaningful statistical analysis. However, neuropathological examination of patient 2 provided strong evidence of target engagement and drug effect, with striking attenuation of abnormal PrP immunoreactivity in the parietal cortex and occipital cortex, markedly altered distribution of disease-related PrP in subventricular areas, and PrP cerebral amyloid angiopathy, which was not seen in untreated patients. We note that amyloid β cerebral amyloid angiopathy has been observed as a consequence of amyloid β monoclonal antibody therapy, but we did not detect amyloid-related imaging abnormalities in any patient. The second patient on whom autopsy was done only received a single dose of 80 mg/kg but also showed altered PrP labelling in periventricular regions. Compared with untreated historical controls, concentrations of tissue-bound drug estimated in post-mortem brain tissue were similar to those in CSF, well in excess of concentrations shown to cure cells of prion infection.^[17]

VIII. DEGRADING MRNA FRAGMENTS, WHILE COUNTERACTING PRIONS AND AMYLOIDS YET AGGREGATED ACTIVITY

In light of this, it would be an opportunity to take advantage of the properties of the anti-PrPC monoclonal antibody **PRN100**, carry out **derivation** and **conjugation** with the **Ranpirnase** enzyme, and then conclude with **optimization** and proceed with the application for the **first phase** of Clinical Trials.

Just as the engineered **derivative** of *Ranpirnase* was made, associating a drug candidate for **non-Hodgkin** lymphomas, called **RFB4-targeted Onconase**, whose specificity for **CD22+ lymphoma** is exploited^[18], inducing good expectations and showing low nonspecific toxicity, it is desirable to be able to create an **Immunornase** agent of the **PRN100 Onc** type, in order to **degrade** the **mRNA** that has now completed its work of immunization against the severe form by **Sars-CoV-2**, avoiding the appearance of **unintended proteins**, and where they are present, it would become possible to **neutralize** them thanks to the properties demonstrated by the **PRN100** antibody.

The **bioengineering process** is delegated from here to specialists in the field who intend to implement a method to **prevent** various forms of **disease**, derived from the persistence of a now **deprecated** mRNA agent.

IX. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The **RNase agents** here described all have various **antitumor** properties through **post-transcriptional** regulation of **cell growth** and **overgrowth**, such as in a tumorigenesis, or **cell death**; the main use of *Ranpirnase* (*Onconase*) involved its to phase III trials in targeting the **malignant mesothelioma (MMe)**.^[13] In addition, many also exert **antiviral** and/or **antimicrobial** activities, of which marked activities may interest the field of research in **anti-HIV** treatments and against new spreading viral **infectious diseases**.

Monoclonal antibodies, despite the difficulty in development and relative rarity of availability for massive uses, are widely researched in the **treatment** of various forms of **cancer, leukemia, autoimmune** diseases, and other serious clinical conditions with **no other** possibility of therapy; this is mainly due to the inherent properties of **high**

targeting receptor capacity (even greater when a **scFv** is used, that is, if the monoclonal antibody is attached to a **single-chain variable fragment** fused together with a third component → see: **scFv 4D5-dibarnase**).^[12]

There is a documented **cytotoxicity** and **cytostatic** effects in the **active elements** in this article presented, which can be exploited for many kinds of treatment and, not least, it is imperative to study about the **toxicity in vitro, in vivo** and **in humans** of the molecules presented, which so far appeared as **very low** or **none**, especially in relation to **dosages**, for use in possible **future scenarios** that will open the door to massive deployment as **mRNA-degrading agents** of **vaccines** and **therapies** of various kinds that as of **2019** represent the **class** of drugs and **preventive** compounds in **infectious diseases** that arouses the most **clinical** and **research** interest.

X. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This study was conducted with the motivation of stopping a new global insidiousness: the persistence of Sars-CoV-2 virus-like symptoms, which in some cases are exacerbated to the point of exitus. Based on the previous study, it was found that the origin of the problem lies in the mRNA of the vaccines themselves, which, after its useful function, must necessarily leave the body, and any misformed proteins must be degraded or rendered harmless, safeguarding the recipient's body from possible onset of pathological matrix.

XI. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The undersigned author declares that there are no conflicts of interest, nor can they be interpreted under any circumstances.

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